

Talent Management Practices and Performance of Lecturers among Federal Universities in South East, Nigeria

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ABSTRACT

The study evaluated the talent management practices and performance of lecturers among Federal Universities in South East, Nigeria. The specific objectives are to: examine the relationship between talent acquisition and retention on the quality of research work among lecturers of the federal universities in South, East Nigeria; evaluate the relationship between salary and quality assurance among lecturers of the federal universities in south East, Nigeria and ascertain the extent of the relationship between succession planning and growth among lecturers of the federal universities in South East, Nigeria between 2008 – 2019. The study used the survey approach. The primary sources were personal interview and the administration of questionnaire. A population of 4525 staff was used. The population of the study was drawn from the groups under study using a stratified sampling method. The adequate sample size of 354, using Freund and William's statistic formula was obtained. 321 staff returned the questionnaire and accurately filled. That gave 91 percent response rate. It gave a reliability co-efficient of 0.75 which was also good. Data was presented and analyzed by mean score (3.0 and above a greed while below 3.0 disagreed) and standard deviation using Sprint Likert Scale. The hypotheses were analyzed using Pearson correlation coefficient (r) statistic tool. The findings indicated that there was positive significance relationship between talent acquisition and retention on the quality of research work among federal universities in South East, Nigeria as reported in the probability value of $r(95, n = 321) = .444, p > 0.05$; there was positive significant relationship between salary and quality assurance among lecturers of the federal universities in South East, Nigeria as reported in the probability value of $r(95, n = 321) = .706, p > 0.05$ and there was positive significant relationship between strategic staff planning and growth among lecturers of the federal universities in South East, Nigeria as reported in the probability value of $r(95, n = 321) = .685, p > 0.05$. The study concluded that talent acquisition, staff development and succession planning had a positive significant relationship with the retention, quality assurance and growth among the lecturers of federal universities in South East, Nigeria. The study recommended among others that Management of the universities should introduce policies that would strengthen the process of enticing, attracting, selecting, fetching, engaging and developing staff with the accurate talent as this would enhance staff flexibility and alertness on the job.

Keywords: Talent Management Practices; Performance of Lecturers; Federal Universities; South-East Nigeria

1. Introduction

Challenges in view of defining, organizing, planning, and evaluation of lecturers in higher institutions in aspects of socialization, acquaintance, and development have generalized attitudinal problems, lack of motivation, and poor performance of students and lecturers in the university. Institutions of higher education and research in various academic disciplines are faced with difficulty in attracting and retaining talented lecturers and staff capable of enhancing the academic objectives in the university and have led to poor performance in the substantive purpose of higher education in teaching, research, and links with society. Management of talents is seen as the solution for challenges in the university as it helps to efficiently organize all administrative processes that emerge in higher institutions. Talent management, when handled strategically, flows from the institution's mission, vision, values, and goals which enable lecturers to fit in within the institution and also participate in the overall direction of the institution (Heathfield, 2019).

Talent management is the systematic process of identifying vacant positions, hiring suitable person, developing skills and expertise of the employee to match the position, and retaining it to achieve long-term business objectives (Ghosh, 2019). Establishing and enhancing proficiency in the university is the mechanism in speeding up growth and development to function in global changes as lecturers of federal universities are faced with the challenges of decreased levels of talent acquisition and retention. Talent management involves individuals and institutional development in response to a changing and complex operating environment. It includes the creation and maintenance of supportive people with oriented organizational culture.

Performance refers to the extent to which organizations achieve the purpose for which it is created and must be analyzed closely to targeted institutions' objectives. Talent management practice strategy in the university boosts the university performances and characterizes the achieved results obtained to enhance lecturers' potentials. Talented individuals are designated based on various attributes such as skills, competencies, experience, knowledge, and ability to learn and grow within the organization (Thunnissen & Buttiens, 2017). Saint (2015) ascertained that University performance is becoming an issue of concern due to the emergence of a knowledge-driven economy in the world that changes the understandings of the role of Universities and other higher institutions of learning to national economic development. The ability of university lecturers to strive in directing the vision of the university, establishing of long-term cooperation, and saving the institutions' knowledge has led to the study of Talent management practices and performance of lecturers among federal Universities in South East, Nigeria.

Statement of Problem

Talent management practices in federal universities are connected to university performance and sustainability. Hence, it is an important aspect in the university that differentiates between lecturers working in the universities and consequently making a significant distinction between a university that is thriving and the one that is stagnant, struggling, or declining as it creates a strategy that could attract potential talents, and in turn, contributes to the improvement of the university performance, results, and achievement. Talent management can also be viewed as an appropriate framework to enable universities to transform their current human resources systems into something that is strategically enabling.

Talent management allows universities to attract the most talented and skilled lecturers available. It creates a brand that could attract potential talents, and in turn, contributes to the improvement of the universities with better performance and results. Poor talent management hinders the capacity and capability to innovate adequate management issues including the inability to expand and complete major projects, difficulties forecasting growth, and a slide in the institution's competitiveness. Notwithstanding the heightened approval of talent management in the university's growth, development and performance, its concept remains unclear as it is faced with challenges in practicing talent acquisition and retention of great talents that will boost organizations objectives, strategies on staff development with the required talent and poor succession planning on how to sustain the organization in agreement with the global change.

University lecturers experiencing vague notions of talent management practices and poor performance do not only sustain the above-mentioned problems but will further encounter the substandard quality of research work, lack of quality assurance, and low growth rate among the students, lecturers, and staff of the universities if the problems are not properly addressed. The issue of ineffective talent management, establishing succession plans for top-level executive positions is one positive step. Therefore, the study tends to evaluate the talent management practices and performance of lecturers among federal universities in southeast, Nigeria.

The objective of the Study

The main objective of the study was to evaluate the talent management practices and performance of lecturers among Federal Universities in South East, Nigeria. The specific objectives are to:

- I. Examine the relationship between talent acquisition and retention on the quality of research work among lecturers of the federal universities in South, East Nigeria.
- II. Evaluate the relationship between staff development and quality assurance among lecturers of the federal universities in South-East, Nigeria.
- III. Ascertain the extent of the relationship between succession planning and growth among lecturers of the federal universities in South East, Nigeria.

Research Questions

The following research questions guided the study

- I. What is the relationship between talent acquisition and retention on the quality of research work among lecturers of the federal universities in South East, Nigeria?
- II. What is the relationship between staff development and quality assurance among lecturers of the federal universities in South East, Nigeria?
- III. To what extent is the relationship between strategic staff planning and growth among lecturers of the federal universities in South East, Nigeria?

Statement of the Hypotheses

The following null hypotheses guided the study

- I. There is no positive significant relationship between talent acquisition and retention on the quality of research work among federal universities in South East, Nigeria
- II. There is no positive significant relationship between staff development and quality assurance among lecturers of the federal universities in South East, Nigeria.
- III. There is no positive significant relationship between strategic staff planning and growth among lecturers of the federal universities in South East, Nigeria.

Significance of the Study

Talent management practices help to prepare an organization for future skills to face challenges competently. The study will be beneficial to the following:

Government: Government personnel will benefit from the study as it shows the impact of in training policy formulation for government parastatals and institutions that will enable organizations to take their employees for talent management sessions or invite the trainers to train employees in their organizations thereby giving the employees opportunity to develop and enhance their skill.

Organizations: Talent management practices help organizations attract and retain the best talent that will boost the organizations' objectives.

Employees: Employees benefit from organizations' talent management practices as it allows them to acquire and develop professional skills. It is also a major motivator to why employees tend to last long in a particular job.

Researchers and Students: students and researchers will benefit from the study as it would add to the body of knowledge on talent and performance and also serve as a reference for researchers and academicians, private and public organizations interested in improving their organizational performance and recruiting the required talents.

2. Review of Related Literature

2.1 Conceptual Framework

Talent Management Practices

Talent management practices in the universities is a strategic system implemented in the university for the sole purpose of attracting, selecting, recruiting, developing, retaining, and utilization of the lecturers to produce quality students. Talent is a desirable quality in all human beings and also an exceptional natural skill possessed by individuals who come without training and enhance the individual's potentials. Talent management practices aid to recognize the worth of knowledge and capabilities in the realization of corporate objectives. Talent management in the university describes the systematic attraction, identification, development, engagement, retention, and deployment of lecturers who are of particular value to the university, either because of their high potential for the future or because of fulfilling operation-critical roles (NHS, 2014). Talent may be either stable or developable (Meyers & Woerkom, 2014).

Talent management practices in the university help to recognize and reward talent throughout all academic, administrative, and management roles. Universities have a primary duty of producing graduates that can be able to accommodate and compete favorably in the societal challenges and also produce a high-quality profile that can greatly compete in the labour market. Implementation of talent management is the fundamental system and process within a university, which relies on the skills and expertise of professional administrators and academic managers (Bradley, 2016). A talent management practice in the university is the appropriate framework that enables the universities to transform their human resources systems into strategically enabling states as they ensure that knowledge is been inculcated in the students with maximum quality service. Talent management helps lecturers reach optimal performance and use, fully their capacity and potential. Mc Cormack, Propper & Smith (2013) found that management practice burst university performance while organizational innovativeness determines performance in the university (Kasim & Noh, 2012) in the study of (Haim & Abubakar, 2017).

Components of Talent Management Practices Used in the Study

Talent Acquisition and Staff Retention

Talent is defined as the unique character that sets one apart from other individuals and also the natural ability of an individual to perform a specific task in a specific way. Retention is the systematic process through which individuals are encouraged to remain within an organization by creating policies that satisfy their needs. Talent acquisition and retention are achieved through identifying, assessing, developing, and retaining people with critical knowledge, skills, and competencies. Talent retention helps an organization to realize its goals through appropriate strategies for individual enhanced performance. Performance and reward programs in higher education are connected to being able to support effective and robust talent management due to the fact that higher education institutions use systematic performance management processes to assess and improve staff performance (Rudhumbu, 2014). Talent acquisition includes attracting, retaining and developing the talent pool available to an organization in other to overcome lack of proficiency.

Shikha (2012) stated that talent is a commodity in short supply and comes at a price. Since it is a scarce resource, it needs to be optimally managed. Higher education institutions should always seek to hire talent which replicates their top performers and are able to fit into the institution's unique culture (Lavanial, Sharma, Gupta, 2011). Capable talents are retained in the organization through motivation, interaction, visioning, and the learning process.

Staff Development

Staff Development is defined as the attempt to improve staff and management effectiveness through a planned and deliberated learning process. Development therefore, is a systematic art of educating managers to enhance managerial as well as organizational effectiveness. It centers more on the education of managers in the various field of management. Therefore, the only distinction between reining and development may be sort along the lines of tine position of the trainees, his level of academic knowledge and the type of job undertaken (Udeh, 2017).

Training and development cannot be ignored by an organization that aspires to increase its productivity. As Nwachukwu (2014) puts it, any organization that lays little or no emphasis on training and development is encouraging the obsolescence of employees, encouraging inflexibility in the organization and appears not to recognize the changing environment in which it operates. Technological innovations taking place everyday renders

today's skills and methods ineffective for tomorrow's activities. Unfortunately, in this part of the world, it has been observed that training and development budgets are haphazardly allocated based on the state of the organization. Most organizations are not doing much when it comes to training their employees.

The level of training and development in Nigeria is very poor and employers are not ready to adequately train their employees. Even the big organizations and multinationals do not invest enough to train the people who work for them. But it is worse with the High institutions because many of them claim that they do not have enough money to train their employees. They are concerned about making money and increasing revenues. They always consider training as the last thing they should think about. They see training as an expense and one of the easiest ways to cut down (Nwachukwu, 2014).

Succession Planning

Succession planning in the university refers to an emergency response plan for the sudden loss of lecturers due to illness, death, or unplanned resignation. It is also a process of identifying and developing lecturers who can replace old lecturers of the university when they leave, retire or die. Succession planning is most generally understood to refer to a long-term framework for developing replacements for senior positions upon the planned departure of the incumbents. Succession planning in the university is a subset of workforce planning with a focus on having the right people, with appropriate attributes, who can transition into Heads of School, Associate Deans, and Deans positions (Archer & Makkai, 2015). Succession planning is part of workforce planning which enables the University to identify talented employees and provide education to develop them for future higher level and broader responsibilities. The objective of succession planning is to ensure that the University continues to operate effectively when individuals occupying critical positions depart.

Performance in the Universities

Performance in the university is the act or process of performing a task or an action. The term performance encompasses economic and behavioral results and is understood as the achievement of an organization in relation to its objective. It includes outcomes achieved or accomplished through the contribution of individuals or teams to the institution's strategic goals.

Samsonowa, (2012), defined performance as the degree of goal achievement of an institution rather than of individuals. The inculcation of academic knowledge, skills, abilities, and proficiency among individuals is enhanced through learning and academic performance (Kapur, 2018).

Performance helps the university lecturer's administration to design and implement policies that will improve the students' performance and the quality of education by changing the attitude of students towards learning, facilitating students, and improving the teaching procedures (Mushtaq, Nawaz & Khan 2012).

The performance of students is affected by communication skills as it is possible to see communication as a variable that may be positively related to the performance of the university lecturers and students in open learning. Performance in the university includes promoting extra classes for lecturers and students, introducing effective teaching-learning methods and instructional strategies, using technology. Rewarding a lecturer for good performance serves as a motivating factor and when low grades are achieved in other to work more to make improvements (Nyagosia, 2011).

Components of Performance Among Lecturers Used in the study

Quality of Research Work

Quality Research work in the university is the creative and systematic work undertaken to increase the stock of knowledge and involves the collection, organizing, and analysis of information to increase the understanding of a topic. Quality research work in the university system is self-regulating and an essential key to continuous evaluation of the academic system in recruiting, publication and funding which helps to create quality assurance in the university lecturers and used worldwide.

Farahmandian, Minavand & Afshardost (2013) noted that Research are important, because student satisfaction is as an indicator of quality in higher education.

Håkan, Åsa & Anders (2014) ascertained that an important feature of the republic of scholars is the professional self-regulation and faculty control over research and teaching, while an important component of the stakeholder organization is the presence of laymen within the university and a stronger focus on university deliverables than on internal procedures. Qualitative studies are understood as proper study process organization and lecturer work and activity quality (Lamanauskas & Petkevičienė, 2016).

The excitement of engaging with the development of the knowledge base of the discipline itself contributes to student learning. The relationship between research and teaching in higher education helps in expert and contemporary knowledge being passed onto the students.

Quality Assurance

Quality assurance in the university is the maintenance of the desired level of quality in service by means of attending to all stages of the process of delivery from the students to lecturers and all management and staffs of the university. Dill, (2010) opined that academic literature has often challenged the need for external quality assurance mechanisms, through which academic quality, mainly internal to higher education institutions, were less effective and outmoded in the context of the changing higher education systems and environments.

Farooq, Chaudhry, Shafiq, Berhanu (2011) noted that the key aspect for quality assurance in higher education is to educate students effectively so that they may be able to show quality performance in their academics. Quality of higher education is one of the most important and pressing issues for the development of lecturers of a higher education system. The three main approaches to quality in higher institutions are accreditation, assessment and audit. Accreditation and evaluation (which includes assessment and audit) differ in their perspectives. Both accreditation and assessment monitor the quality of teaching and learning, while audit focuses on internal procedures adopted in order to achieve its objectives.

Growth in the Universities

Growth in the university refers to academic progress made over a period of time, from the beginning to the end of the defined period. Successful universities are capable of being nimble, anticipatory, imaginative and reactive. For growth in the university, Universities need to foster student success by becoming student centric rather than faculty centric (Crow, 2014). Growth in the university is applicable to staff, lecturers and students performance.

Heggart (2015) noted that fixed mindset people dread failure, feeling that it reflects badly upon themselves as individuals, while growth mindset people instead embrace failure as an opportunity to learn and improve their abilities. Universities could promote strong institutions directly by providing a platform for democratic dialogue and sharing of ideas, through events, publications, or reports to policy makers (Valero & Reenen, 2019). Participating in workshops, seminars, conferences and sharing of ideas enhances growth among lecturers in the university.

2.2 Theoretical Framework

The Social Exchange theory and Theory of organizational Equilibrium guided the study

Theory of Organizational Equilibrium

One of the earliest models of turnover is March and Simon's (1958) theory of organizational equilibrium, in which the authors proposed that desirability of movement and ease of movement are the two main drivers of employee turnover. Desirability of movement is commonly defined by the individual's satisfaction with the job, whereas ease of movement generally reflects perceived or actual job alternatives in the external market (Lawler, 2001). Viewed from the perspective of retention, the model suggests that employees will be more likely to stay when they are satisfied with their jobs and believe that there are few alternatives available. Hence, job satisfaction and lack of alternatives are included here as two important factors in employees' decisions to stay. Employees would be satisfied (and thus more likely to stay) if they felt that the outcomes they received reflected the effort and other inputs that they had invested. More recently, organizational justice has been defined more broadly to include fairness perceptions related to outcomes, procedures, and interpersonal interactions, which have been shown to be related to employees' decisions to remain with their employer (Aquino, Griffeth, Allen, & Hom, 1997).

Social Exchange Theory (George Homans)

Social exchange theory proposes that social behavior is the result of an exchange process. The purpose of this exchange is to maximize benefits and minimize costs. According to this theory, developed by sociologist George

Homans, people weigh the potential benefits and risks of social relationships. When the risks outweigh the rewards, people will terminate or abandon that relationship. Most relationships are made up of a certain amount of give-and-take, but this does not mean that they are always equal. Social exchange suggests that it is the valuing of the benefits and costs of each relationship that determine whether or not we choose to continue a social association (Kendra, 2020).

Central to the social exchange theory is the idea that an interaction that elicits approval from another person is more likely to be repeated than an interaction that elicits disapproval. We can thus predict whether a particular interaction will be repeated by calculating the degree of reward (approval) or punishment (disapproval) resulting from the interaction. If the reward for an interaction exceeds the punishment, then the interaction is likely to occur or continue (Ashley, 2020).

2.3 Empirical Review by Objectives

The Relationship between Talent Acquisition and Retention on the Quality of Research Work Among Lecturers of the Federal Universities in South East, Nigeria

Aibieyi & Oghoator, (2015) conducted a study on Talent Management and Employees Retention in Nigerian Universities. The purpose of the study was to examine the relationship between talent management and employee retention. Talent management is represented by performance management, employee's empowerment, compensation and reward. While employee's retention is represented by organizational culture. The study employed primary source of data through administered questionnaires and Secondary sources of data were also used while reviewing related literature. Test of equality, Pearson correlation and ordinary least square regression techniques were utilized for the data analysis. The result indicated that performance management ($X_1=2.09$) was significant and positively related to organizational culture. Employee empowerment (X_2) was significant and negatively related to organizational culture. Compensation and reward ($X_3=52$) was positive and had insignificant impact on organizational culture. The study concluded that the benefits derived from talent management include reduced hiring cost, a well negotiated salary structure; efficient and effective inspired and committed team and consequently improved efficiency in service delivery. The study therefore recommended that universities should adopt a proactive performance management system to have a more transparent and dynamic institutional culture so as to encourage and retain skillful and talented employees.

Korantwi-Barimah (2017) carried out a study on the factors influencing the Retention of Academic Staff in Ghanaian Technical University. The constant loss of quality academic staff has become a matter of great concern to management of Ghanaian universities. The main objective of the study was to identify factors that influence the retention of academic staff in Sunyani Technical University, Ghana. A qualitative research design involving an interview with academic staff of the university was followed. Nine academic staff were purposefully selected to provide understanding into factors they perceived to be important in their retention. A content analysis of the data resulted in clusters of themes that addressed the research objective. The study found that the factors that appeared to influence the retention of the university's academic staff were identified as: leadership and institutional culture, growth opportunities, institutional mission and vision, meaningful work and collegiality. The study recommends that the university translates these factors into formal retention strategies based on the intrinsic needs of staff and also leverages on the strengths provided by its institutional culture. The practical value of this study has been the highlighting of the factors that can be leveraged to retain the institution's academic staff. The study contributes empirical findings on staff retention in a Ghanaian university, a research area in which there is a scarcity of empirical studies.

Alagah & Tende, Buradum (2017) conducted a study on Talent Retention and Organizational Agility of Insurance Companies in Port Harcourt, Nigeria. The study sought to examine the nexus between talent retention and organizational agility of insurance companies in Port Harcourt. 102 managers and supervisors were drawn from the population size of 140 using Krejcie and Morgan (1970) sample size determination table for the ten insurance companies for the study. Two testable null hypotheses were formulated from the variables. Spearman's Rank Order Correlation Coefficient was employed to analyze the null hypotheses, via the aid of Statistical Package for Social Sciences at 5% level of significance. 99 copies of the questionnaire were retrieved and analyzed out of the 102 copies of the questionnaire administered. All the null hypotheses were rejected and the alternate accepted. Hence the study found that talent retention significantly influences organizational agility in insurance companies in Port

Harcourt. The study concluded that for insurance agencies to survive, grow, and make profit, it should source, hire, and retain valuable relevant talents, and should patiently take them through talent development programmes that would help improve both flexible and responsive capabilities among employees in insurance companies in Port Harcourt. It was thus recommended that management of insurance agencies should introduce policies that would strengthen the process of enticing, attracting, selecting, fetching, engaging and developing employees with the accurate talent as this would enhance employee flexibility and alertness on the job.

The Relationship between Staff Development and Quality Assurance among Lecturers of the Federal Universities in South East, Nigeria

Maryam, Naveed, Nadeem, Zeeshan and Naqvi (2014) carried out a review on the impact of training and development on the employee performance: a case study from different banking sectors of North Punjab. The purpose of this study is to find out the impact of employee training and development on employee's performance. The results show that significant positive relationship exists between employee training and development and the employee performance. The statistical population of this study is Banking Sector of northern Punjab which covers 100 employees of 11 banks and data was collected through a questionnaire. Regression analysis was used through "SPSS" for data analysis. There are two determinants of employee training and development which are on job Training and Delivery style. Results show the Positive relationship between on job Training and Employee performance and also there is the Positive relationship between Delivery style and Employee Performance.

Halidu, (2015) carried out an empirical review on the impact of training and development on workers' productivity in some selected Nigerian universities. Staff training and development is a key to achieving organizational success and corporate development. The study is aimed at finding out the Impact of Training and Development on workers' productivity via the Tertiary Education Trust Fund (TET Fund) Academic Staff Training & Development 2010 Sponsorship of some selected Nigerian universities. The study hypothesized that there is no significant relationship between training and workers productivity. Results revealed that training and development programs improve employees' skills and performance at work place, enhance their technical knowhow/ wherewithal to withstand the challenges of contemporary times, thus, an effective tool for sustaining and enhancing workers productivity in the academia. The study recommends that Tertiary Education Trust Fund should improve on its training policy in its entire ramification because in recent times academics are being faced with new innovations and techno- scientific developments so as to meet up with the changing trends and circumstances.

Isiwu (2012) carried out a studied on the impact of staff training in the productivity of workers in public sector in Nigeria: A Case Study of Personnel Services Department University of Nigeria, Nsukka from 2000-2010. Every organization whether public or private, at every instance desire to satisfy the needs of its clients, this will only be possible with an enlightened and well-trained staff therefore, the role played by staff training cannot be over-emphasized as many have come to recognize that training offers a way of developing skill, enhancing productivity, guaranteeing quality of work and build worker's loyalty to the firm. The work was guided by the following research questions What are the factors that determine the training of Staff of personnel services department University of Nigeria Nsukka? Does training of the Staff of personnel Service department of University of Nigeria Nsukka bring about improved productivity? What are the factors that can hinder the training of Staff of the personnel Service department of University of Nigeria Nsukka? How can the needs be effectively filled to improve performance of Staff of the personnel services department of University of Nigeria Nsukka? Stratified random sampling was used in this study and the sample size of 101 was used and analyzed. Questionnaire was used as the method of data collection and simple percentage was used as the method of data analyses.

The findings for this study include the following; training and performance appraisal should be done frequently for staff on organizations, staff who are found guilty of an offence should be dismissed, staff whose productivity is low should be disciplined, training should not be made compulsory for staff, there was improvement in the performance of staff of personnel services department within the period under study. Some recommendation includes that management should always detect training needs, organizations should constantly embark on performance appraisal, the code of conduct and ethics of the profession should be strictly adhered, underperforming staff should be punished.

The Extent of the Relationship between Strategic Staff Planning and Growth among Lecturers of the Federal Universities in South East, Nigeria

Akinyele & Fasogbon (2007) Examined the Impact of Strategic Planning on Organizational Performance and Survival. The study examined the impact of strategic planning on organizational performance and survival. The effectiveness of strategic planning can be measured in terms of the extent to which it influences organizational performance, which affects its survival rate. The main objective of the study was to re-evaluate the planning-performance relationship in organization and determine the extent to which strategic planning affects performance in an organization, of which First Bank of Nigeria, Plc (FBN) will be used as case study. Based on the above objective, relevant literatures were thoroughly reviewed and three hypotheses were formulated and tested in this study.

A survey technique was used with the administration of questionnaires to 100 respondents (of which 80 was retrieved) comprising of both the senior and junior staff in various First bank branches in Lagos metropolis. The data collected were analyzed using the Statistical Package for Social Sciences (SPSS). Also, T-Test and Chi-square statistical methods were used in testing the hypotheses using the SPSS. The three hypotheses were confirmed. For the purpose of testing for reliability of the instrument, 'The Split-Half Technique' from SPSS was used. The implication of the study is that Strategic planning enhances better organizational performance, which in the long run has impact on its survival and that strategic planning intensity is determined by managerial, environmental and organizational factors.

Thomas & Schlump (2010) investigated University Education, Public Research and Employment Growth in Regions. An Empirical Study of Germany. Universities and research institutes are seen as important drivers of the regional economy. Their impact on regional entrepreneurial and innovation activity is well documented. On the other hand, their influence on regional employment growth is less researched. The study aimed to provides an extensive empirical analysis of the relationship between the education of university graduates and employees in research institutes and the growth of employment in a region. The analysis is done for nine industries separately. The study found that university graduates have a significant influence on employment growth in several industries, while an influence of public research institutes is found only for a few industries. For most control variables the findings differ between manufacturing and service industries. Such a clear difference between the two types of industries is not found for university graduates and public research institutes.

Otaigbe & Ijeh (2015) conducted a study on Strategic Planning as an Effective Tool on Organizational Performance in Nigeria: An Empirical Study of Some Firms in Delta State. The study was carried out to investigate the impact of strategic planning on organizational performance. A study of selected manufacturing firms in Delta State, Nigeria. A set of structural questionnaires was used as instrument for data collection and administered on 60 respondents of the firms under study randomly selected using Yaro yamane formula. Applying the formula, the sample size from a population of 70 is 60 respondents at 95% confidence level. Data analysis was made and the hypotheses formulated were tested using kruskal wall is one-way analysis of variance by rank. The findings revealed that positive and significant relationship exists between strategic planning and better organizational performance and organizational survival. The study concluded that strategic planning is necessary for the performance and survival of an organization. The study, however, recommend that organizations should accord priority attention to the elements of strategic planning, establishing high core values that is organizations rules of conduct, set realistic goals, establishment of long term objective, this has to be measurable and specific, the development of action (strategic) plans and its implementation, making adequate environmental analysis, suitable organizational structure and a host of other measures for effective strategic planning kin organizations.

3. Methodology

The study comprised of the relationship between talent management practices and performance of lecturers in Federal universities of south east Nigeria. The universities are: Federal university of Agriculture, Umudike, Abia state, Nnamdi Azikwe University, Awka, Anambra state, Federal university of Agriculture, Ndufu Aleke, Ebonyi state, University of Nigeria, Nsukka, Enugu state and Federal university of Technology, Owerri, Imo state between 2017 – 2020. The study used the survey design approach.

The primary sources were personal interview and the administration of questionnaire. A population of 4525 staff was used. The population of the study was drawn from the groups under study using a stratified sampling method. The adequate sample size of 354, using Freund and William's statistic formula was obtained. 321 staff returned the questionnaire and accurately filled. That gave 91 percent response rate. The validity of the instrument was tested

using content analysis and the result was good. The reliability was tested using the Pearson correlation coefficient (r). It gave a reliability co-efficient of 0.75 which was also good. Data was presented and analyzed by mean score (3.0 and above a greed while below 3.0 disagreed) and standard deviation using Sprint Likert Scale. The hypotheses were analyzed using Pearson correlation coefficient (r) statistics tool

4. Presentation and Analysis

Table 4.1 Responses on the Relationship between Talent Acquisition and Retention on the Quality of Research Work among Lecturers of Federal Universities in South East, Nigeria.

		5 SA	4 A	3 N	2 DA	1 SD	ΣFX	- X	SD	Decision
1	Engaging current and potential employees in my institution produce high quality research that produces knowledge that is applicable outside of the research setting.	420 84 26.2	668 167 52.0	69 23 7.2	52 26 8.1	21 21 6.5	1230 321 100%	3.83	1.105	Agree
2	Extending hot skill bonuses in my institutions encourages the research that is replicable and doable	690 138 43.0	148 37 11.5	144 48 15.0	36 18 5.6	80 80 24.9	1098 321 100%	3.42	1.649	Agree
3	The attractive compensation packages encourage staff in a research that is generalisable to other settings	585 117 36.4	124 31 9.7	144 48 15.0	34 17 5.0	108 108 33.6	995 321 100%	3.10	1.718	Agree
4	Having a holistic work opportunity to staff enhances a research that is incremental in my institution	575 115 35.8	180 45 14.0	93 31 9.7	74 37 11.5	93 93 29.0	1015 321 100%	3.16	1.682	Agree
5	The filling of future leadership roles and keeping costs of replacement down has encouraged quality research work.	295 59 18.4	476 119 37.1	144 48 15.0	46 23 7.2	72 72 22.4	1033 321 100	3.21	1.426	Agree
	Total Grand mean and standard deviation							3.34	1.52	

Source: Field Survey, 2020

In table 4.1, 251 respondents out of 321 representing 78.2 percent agreed that engaging current and potential employees in my institution produce high quality research that produces knowledge that is applicable outside of the research setting with mean score of 3.83 and standard deviation of 1.105. Extending hot skill bonuses in my institutions encourages the research that is replicable and doable with 175 respondents representing 54.5 percent agreed with mean score of 3.42 and standard deviation of 1.649. The attractive compensation packages encourage staff in a research that is generalisable to other settings with 148 respondents representing 46.1 percent agreed with mean score of 3.10 and standard deviation of 1.718. Having a holistic work opportunity to staff enhances a research that is incremental in my institution with 160 respondents representing 49.8 percent agreed with mean score of 3.16 and 1.682. The filling of future leadership roles and keeping costs of replacement down has encouraged quality research work with 178 respondents representing 55.5 percent agreed with a mean score of 3.21 and standard deviation of 1.426.

Table 4.2 Responses on the Relationship between Staff Development and Quality Assurance among Lecturers of Federal Universities in South East, Nigeria

		5 SA	4 A	3 N	2 DA	1 SD	ΣFX	- X	SD	Decision
1	More of the staff needs are met and build a positive reputation for reliability in my institution	355 71 22.1	420 105 32.7	126 42 13.1	76 38 11.8	65 65 20.2	1042 321 100%	3.25	1.444	Agree
2	There is consistency in training and enhancement quality services in my institution	410 82 25.5	296 74 23.1	144 48 19.3	128 64 20.2	39 39 11.8	1017 321 100%	3.17	1.463	Agree
3	The training in my institution increases my institution meeting the expectations	415 83 25.9	292 73 22.7	186 62 19.3	76 38 11.8	65 65 20.2	1034 321 100%	3.22	1.466	Agree
4	High imparted knowledge in my institution compared to state universities builds trusts and provide confidence to deliver	20 4 60.3	608 152 9.4	195 65 15.8	76 38 12.6	62 62 1.9	961 328 100%	2.92	1.206	Agree
5	High skills and attitude acquired compels a staff to do a good job and be retained in his position in my institution	255 51 15.9	400 100 31.2	162 54 16.8	76 38 11.8	78 78 24.3	971 321 100	3.02	1.429	Agree
	Total Grand mean and standard deviation							3.11	1.40	

Source: Field Survey, 2020

In table 4.2, 176 respondents out of 321 representing 54.8 percent agreed that more of the staff needs are met and build a positive reputation for reliability in my institution with mean score of 3.25 and standard deviation of 1.444. There is consistency in training and enhancement quality services in my institution with 156 respondents representing 48.6 percent agreed with mean score of 3.17 and standard deviation of 1.463. The training in my institution increases my institutional meeting the expectations with 156 respondents representing 48.6 percent agreed with mean score of 3.22 and standard deviation of 1.466. High imparted knowledge in my institution compared to state universities builds trusts and provide confidence to deliver with 156 respondents representing 69.7 percent agreed with mean score of 2.92 and 1.206 standard deviation. High skills and attitude acquired compels a staff to do a good job and be retained in his position in my institution with 151 respondents representing 47.1 percent agreed with a mean score of 3.02 and standard deviation of 1.429.

Table 4.3 The Extent of the Relationship between Succession Planning and the Growth of Lecturers of Federal Universities in South East, Nigeria

		5 SA	4 A	3 N	2 DA	1 SD	ΣFX	- X	SD	Decision
1	There is identification of key roles in my institution that maintains brand identity.	750 130 40.5	140 35 10.9	186 62 19.3	76 38 11.8	56 56 17.4	1208 321 100%	3.76	1.532	Agree
2	There are people with the right skills in my institution that creates structure for training and development	70 14 4.4	604 151 47.0	180 60 18.2	80 40 12.0	56 56 17.4	990 321 100%	3.08	1.207	Agree
3	There is a way to cut the costs of recruitment in my institution that keeps the staff extra eyes on another job	250 50 15.6	520 130 40.5	192 64 19.7	72 36 11.4	41 41 12.8	1075 321 100%	3.35	1.243	Agree
4	My institution manages recruitment in-house that helps to identify most qualified future leaders in my institution	790 158 49.2	88 22 6.9	186 62 19.3	76 38 11.8	41 41 12.8	1181 321 100%	3.68	1.487	Agree
5	Succession planning helps my institution plan for the long - term.	695 139 43.3	160 40 12.5	186 62 19.3	48 24 7.5	56 56 17.4	1145 321 100	3.57	1.522	Agree
	Total Grand mean and standard deviation							3.49	1.40	

Source: Field Survey, 2020

In table 4.3, 165 respondents out of 321 representing 51.4 percent agreed that There is identification of key roles in my institution that maintains brand identity with mean score of 3.76 and standard deviation of 1.532. There are people with right skills in my institution that creates structure for training and development with 165 respondents representing 51.4 percent agreed with mean score of 3.08 and standard deviation of 1.207. There is a way to cut the costs of recruitment in my institution that keeps the staff extra eyes on their job with 180 respondents representing 56.1 percent agreed with mean score of 3.35 and standard deviation of 1.243. My institution manage recruitment in-house that helps to identify most qualified future leaders in my institution with 180 respondents representing 56.1 percent agreed with mean score of 3.68 and 1.487. Succession planning helps my institution plan for the long - term with 179 respondents representing 55.8 percent agreed with a mean score of 3.57 and standard deviation of 1.522.

Test of Hypotheses

Hypothesis One:

There is no significance positive relationship between talent acquisition and retention on the quality of research work among federal universities in South East, Nigeria. (See Contingency table Appendix I).

Table 4.4 Pearson Correlation on Hypotheses one

		Engaging current and potential employees in my institution produce high quality research that produce knowledge that is applicable outside of the research setting.	Extending hot skill bonuses in my institutions encourages the research that is replicable and doable	The attractive compensation packages encourage staff that is generalisable to other settings	Having a holistic work opportunity to staff enhances a research that is incremental in my institution	The filling of future leadership roles and keeping costs of replacement down has encouraged quality research work.
Engaging current and potential employees in my institution produce high quality research that produce knowledge that is applicable outside of the research setting.	Pearson Correlation	1	.138*	.011	-.153**	-.165**
	Sig. (2-tailed)		.013	.851	.006	.003
	N	321	321	321	321	321
Extending hot skill bonuses in my institutions encourages the research that is replicable and doable	Pearson Correlation	.138*	1	.774**	.593**	.322**
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.013		.000	.000	.000
	N	321	321	321	321	321
The attractive compensation packages encourage staff that is generalisable to other settings	Pearson Correlation	.011	.774**	1	.828**	.607**
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.851	.000		.000	.000
	N	321	321	321	321	321
Having a holistic work opportunity to staff enhances a research that is incremental in my institution	Pearson Correlation	-.153**	.593**	.828**	1	.710**
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.006	.000	.000		.000
	N	321	321	321	321	321
The filling of future leadership roles and keeping costs of replacement down has encouraged quality research work.	Pearson Correlation	-.165**	.322**	.607**	.710**	1
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.003	.000	.000	.000	
	N	321	321	321	321	321
*. Correlation is significant at the 0.05 level (2-tailed).						

Table 4.4 is the Pearson correlation matrix on the there is no significant positive relationship between talent acquisition and retention on the quality of research work among federal universities showing the correlation coefficients, significant values and the number of cases. The correlation coefficient shows .011<.828. This value indicates that correlation is significant at 0.05 level (2 tailed) and implies that there is significant positive relationship between talent acquisition and retention on the quality of research work among federal universities in South East, Nigeria ($r = .011 < .828$). The computed correlations coefficient is greater than the table value of $r = .195$ with 879 degree of freedom at alpha level for a two-tailed test ($r = .011 < .828, p > .05$).

Decision Rule

The decision rule is to accept the null hypothesis if the computed r is less than the tabulated r, otherwise reject the null hypothesis.

Decision

Since the computed $r = 0.11 < .828$ is greater than the table value of .195, we reject the null hypothesis. Therefore, we concluded that there is significant positive relationship between talent acquisition and retention on the quality of research work among federal universities in South East, Nigeria as reported in the probability value of ($r = .011 < .828, p > .05$).

Test for Hypothesis Two

There is no positive significant relationship between staff development and quality assurance among lecturers of the federal universities in South East, Nigeria (See contingency table Appendix I).

Table 4.5 Pearson Correlation on Hypotheses Two

		More of the staff needs are met and build a positive reputation for reliability in my institution	There is consistency in payment and enhancement quality services in my institution	The additional perks in my institution and this increases my institutional meeting the expectations	High wages in my institution compared to state universities builds trusts and provide confidence to deliver	High salary compels a staff to do a good job and be retained in his position in my institution
More of the staff needs are met and build a positive reputation for reliability in my institution	Pearson Correlation	1	.977**	.854**	.952**	.746**
	Sig. (2-tailed)		.000	.000	.000	.000
	N	321	321	321	321	321
There is consistency in payment and enhancement quality services in my institution	Pearson Correlation	.977**	1	.870**	.959**	.754**
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000		.000	.000	.000
	N	321	321	321	321	321
The additional perks in my institution and this increases my institutional meeting the expectations	Pearson Correlation	.854**	.870**	1	.945**	.588**
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000	.000		.000	.000
	N	321	321	321	321	321
High wages in my institution compared to state universities builds trusts and provide confidence to deliver	Pearson Correlation	.952**	.959**	.945**	1	.673**
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000	.000	.000		.000
	N	321	321	321	321	321
High salary compels a staff to do a good job and be retained in his position in my institution	Pearson Correlation	.746**	.754**	.588**	.673**	1
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000	.000	.000	.000	
	N	321	321	321	321	321

** . Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).

Table 4.5 is the Pearson correlation matrix on the there is no positive significant relationship between staff development and quality assurance among lecturers of the federal universities showing the correlation coefficients, significant values, and the number of cases. The correlation coefficient shows $.588 < .977$. This value indicates that correlation is significant at 0.05 level (2 tailed) and implies that there is a significant positive relationship between

staff development and quality assurance among lecturers of the federal universities in South East, Nigeria ($r = 0.588 < .977$). The computed correlations coefficient is greater than the table value of $r = .195$ with 879 degree of freedom at alpha level for a two-tailed test ($r = .588 < .977, p > .05$).

Decision Rule

The decision rule is to accept the null hypothesis if the computed r is less than the tabulated r , otherwise reject the null hypothesis.

Decision

Since the computed $r = .588 < .977$ is greater than the table value of $.195$, we reject the null hypothesis. Therefore, we concluded that there is significant positive relationship between **staff development** and quality assurance among lecturers of the federal universities in South East, Nigeria as reported in the probability value of ($r = .588 < .977, p > .05$).

Test for Hypothesis Three

There is no positive significant relationship between succession planning and growth among lecturers of the federal universities in South East, Nigeria. (See contingency table Appendix I).

		There is identification of key roles in my institution that maintains brand identity.	There are people with right skills in my institution that creates structure for training and development	There is a way to cut the costs of recruitment in my institution that keeps the staff extra eyes on another job	My institution manage recruitment in-house that helps to identify most qualified future leaders in my institution	Succession planning helps my institution plan for the long - term.
There is identification of key roles in my institution that maintains brand identity.	Pearson Correlation	1	.966**	.739**	.837**	.864**
	Sig. (2-tailed)		.000	.000	.000	.000
	N	321	321	321	321	321
There are people with right skills in my institution that creates structure for training and development	Pearson Correlation	.966**	1	.779**	.810**	.872**
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000		.000	.000	.000
	N	321	321	321	321	321
There is a way to cut the costs of recruitment in my institution that keeps the staff extra eyes on another job	Pearson Correlation	.739**	.779**	1	.934**	.693**
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000	.000		.000	.000
	N	321	321	321	321	321
My institution manage recruitment in-house that helps to identify most qualified future leaders in my institution	Pearson Correlation	.837**	.810**	.934**	1	.735**
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000	.000	.000		.000
	N	321	321	321	321	321
Succession planning helps my institution plan for the long - term.	Pearson Correlation	.864**	.872**	.693**	.735**	1
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000	.000	.000	.000	
	N	321	321	321	321	321

** . Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).

Table 4.6 is the Pearson correlation matrix on the there is no positive significant relationship between strategic staff planning and growth among lecturers of the federal universities showing the correlation coefficients, significant values and the number of cases. The correlation coefficient shows $.693 < .966$. This value indicates that correlation is significant at 0.05 level (2 tailed) and implies that there is significant positive relationship between strategic staff planning and growth among lecturers of the federal universities in South East, Nigeria ($r = .693 < .966$). The computed correlations coefficient is greater than the table value of $r = .195$ with 879 degree of freedom at alpha level for a two-tailed test ($r = .693 < .966, p > .05$).

Decision Rule

The decision rule is to accept the null hypothesis if the computed r is less than the tabulated r , otherwise reject the null hypothesis.

Decision

Since the computed $r = .693 < .966$ is greater than the table value of $.195$, we reject the null hypothesis. Therefore, we concluded that there is significant positive relationship between strategic staff planning and growth among lecturers of the federal universities in South East, Nigeria as reported in the probability value of ($r = .693 < .966, p > .05$).

Discussion of Findings

There is significance positive relationship between talent acquisition and retention on the quality of research work among federal universities in South East, Nigeria

In test of hypotheses one, the result showed that the computed $r = .011 < .828$ is greater than the table value of $.195$, we reject the null hypothesis. Therefore, we concluded that there is significance positive relationship between talent acquisition and retention on the quality of research work among federal universities in South East, Nigeria as reported in the probability value of ($r = .011 < .828, p > .05$).

Aibieyi & Oghoator, (2015) in support of the result in literature review, conducted a study on Talent Management and Employees Retention in Nigerian Universities. The study concluded that the benefits derived from talent management include reduced hiring cost, a well negotiated salary structure; efficient and effective inspired and committed team and consequently improved efficiency in service delivery. Furthermore, Korantwi-Barimah (2017) carried out a study on the factors influencing the Retention of Academic Staff in Ghanaian Technical University. The study found that the factors that appeared to influence the retention of the university's academic staff were identified as: leadership and institutional culture, growth opportunities, institutional mission and vision, meaningful work and collegiality.

There is significant positive relationship between staff development and quality assurance among lecturers of the federal universities in South East, Nigeria

In test of hypotheses two, the result showed that the computed $r = .588 < .977$ is greater than the table value of $.195$. Therefore, we concluded that there is significant positive relationship between staff development and quality assurance among lecturers of the federal universities in South East, Nigeria as reported in the probability value of ($r = .588 < .977, p > .05$).

Usman, Akbar & Ramzan (2013), in the literature review conducted a study on the staff development and Stress on Job Satisfaction of Teachers in District Sialkot, Pakistan. The study concluded that management of colleges should pay attention to training of the teachers to increase job satisfaction of the teachers.

There is significant positive relationship between strategic staff planning and growth among lecturers of the federal universities in South East, Nigeria

In test of hypotheses three, the result showed that the computed $r = .693 < .966$ is greater than the table value of $.195$. Therefore, we concluded that there is significant positive relationship between strategic staff planning and growth among lecturers of the federal universities in South East, Nigeria as reported in the probability value of ($r = .693 < .966, p > .05$).

Akinyele & Fasogbon (2007), in the literature review, Examined the Impact of Strategic Planning on Organizational Performance and Survival. The implication of the study is that Strategic planning enhances better organizational performance, which in the long run has impact on its survival and that strategic planning intensity is determined by managerial, environmental and organizational factors. Moreover, Otaigbe & Ijeh (2015) conducted a study in support of result on Strategic Planning as an Effective Tool on Organizational Performance in Nigeria: An Empirical Study of Some Firms in Delta State. The findings revealed that positive and significant relationship exists between strategic planning and better organizational performance and organizational survival. The study concluded that strategic planning is necessary for the performance and survival of an organization.

Findings of the Study

The findings of the study include;

- I. In test of hypotheses one, the result showed that the computed $r = 0.11 < 0.828$, is greater than the table value of $.195$, we reject the null hypothesis. Therefore, we concluded that there is significant positive relationship between talent acquisition and retention on the quality of research work among federal universities in South East, Nigeria as reported in the probability value of ($r=0.11 < 0.828$, $p > .05$).
- II. In test of hypotheses two, the result showed that the computed $r = .588 < .977$ is greater than the table value of $.195$. Therefore, we concluded that there is significant positive relationship between staff development and quality assurance among lecturers of the federal universities in South East, Nigeria as reported in the probability value of ($r=.588 < .977$, $p > .05$).
- III. In test of hypotheses three, the result showed that the computed $r = .693 < .966$, is greater than the table value of $.195$. Therefore, we concluded that there is significant positive relationship between strategic staff planning and growth among lecturers of the federal universities in South East, Nigeria as reported in the probability value of ($r=.693 < .966$, $p > .05$).

5. Conclusion

The study concluded that talent acquisition and retention, staff development and strategic planning had positive significant relationship with the quality of research work, quality assurance, growth among lecturers of the federal universities in South East, Nigeria. Talent management focuses on how to develop and guide university lecturers and students. Universities provide learning opportunities and tools for students, lecturers and researchers to advance their overall careers. Managing talents is one of the best ways to ensure that higher institutions have the leadership it will need for a successful future. Few institutions have a sufficient supply of talent. Gaps exist in every organization and talent is more and scarcer, so it needs to be managed. Talent is developed in numerous ways other than just traditional training and development. It can be obtained by coaching, job shadowing, lectures, mentoring, rotations, books, articles, assessments, and more (Marius, 2017).

6. Recommendation

Based on the study the following recommendations were made:

- I. Management of the universities should introduce policies that would strengthen the process of enticing, attracting, selecting, fetching, engaging and developing staff with the accurate talent as this would enhance staff flexibility and alertness on the job.
- II. Future studies should increase the sample size and focus on different schools and disciplines in the university.
- III. The universities should pay priority attention to the elements of strategic planning, establishing high core values that are university rules of conduct, set realistic goals, establishment of long-term objective.

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Appendix I

CONTINGENCY TABLES

Research Question One

S/N	<i>The relationship between talent acquisition and retention on the quality of research work among lecturers of federal universities in south east, Nigeria</i>	SA	A	N	D	SD
1.	Engaging current and potential employees in my institution produce high quality research that produces knowledge that is applicable outside of the research setting.	84	167	23	26	21
2.	Extending hot skill bonuses in my institutions encourages the research that is replicable and doable	138	37	48	18	80
3.	The attractive compensation packages encourage staffs in a research that is generalisable to other settings	117	31	48	17	108
4.	Having a holistic work opportunity to staff enhances a research that is incremental in my institution	115	45	31	37	93
5.	The filling of future leadership roles and keeping costs of replacement down has encouraged quality research work.	59	119	48	23	72

Research Question Two

S/N	<i>The relationship between salary and quality assurance among lecturers of federal universities in south east, Nigeria in south east, Nigeria</i>	SA	A	N	D	SD
1.	More of the staff needs are met and build a positive reputation for reliability in my institution	71	105	42	38	65
2.	There is consistency in training and enhancement quality services in my institution	82	74	48	64	39
3.	The training in my institution increases my institution meeting the expectations	83	73	62	38	65
4.	High imparted knowledge in my institution compared to state universities builds trusts and provide confidence to deliver	4	152	65	38	62
5.	High skills and attitude acquired compels a staff to do a good job and be retained in his position in my institution	51	100	54	38	78

Research Question Three

S/N	<i>The relationship between succession planning and the growth of lecturers of federal universities in south east, Nigeria in south east, Nigeria</i>	SA	A	N	D	SD
1.	There is identification of key roles in my institution that maintains brand identity	130	35	62	38	56
2.	There are people with right skills in my institution that creates structure for training and development	14	151	60	40	56
3.	There is a way to cut the costs of recruitment in my institution that keeps the staff extra eyes on their job	50	130	64	36	41
4.	My institution manage recruitment in-house that helps to identify most qualified future leaders in my institution	158	22	62	38	41
5.	Succession planning helps my institution plan for the long-term	139	40	62	24	56